

EDUCATION POLICIES LAWS AND ITS OUTPUT TOWARDS SC ST AND OBC IN INDIA

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Introduction:

Ancient education policy, current education policy and upcoming education policy 2020 which is being implemented into over all India. All Policies are totally different according to their stated objectives. But one thing is common towards build of society and its output. It is seemed value base education but output shows discrimination into implementation. Example, ratio of SC ST OBC in higher post, in Class one and Class two post is not adequate as per their population. Reservation was the one policy to give proper and adequate representation to these wicker section, suppressed people whose population in India is 85 %. These people has no decision making power and any power to implement the welfare policy for these huge population. All the implemented power is isolated in the hands of policy maker. Who is policy maker ? only upper cast or Three varna people accumulated power, wealth, legislature, judiciary, executive and media. Value base education was sabotaged by Varna system and its graded inequality. The traditional attitude towards education policy is there.

Keywords: *Education policy Socio, Economic, Varna, System, Class*

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Objective of the study:

1. To study socio economic system though education policy of India
2. To know the present scenario of output of education
3. To know to the mechanism of governing class

Data Collection:

There are two types of data i. e. primary data and secondary data. Here secondary data is used. All data are collected from secondary data. Various books, reports, web sites, news paper etc. are the source of secondary date which has been used.

Scope and limitation of the study:

The research paper is having base of secondary data. It is related socio economic study of the Indian people. Social and economic system of India is analyzed with the help of books reports news paper etc. so the research paper is limited up to social and economic study of Indian people and governing class.

Introduction:

OBC means other backward class. It is noted in article no. 340 of constitution of India. Obc is nothing but shudra varna and it is kept at bottom level. It do not have right of taking education, giving education, accumulating wealth etc. There are three types of OBC in independence India.

One is come under the brahmin. This obc is very religious and pay respect to vaidik culture which imposed by Brahmin. Satya Narayan, Marriage of Tulsi, Duraga Puja, Diwali, Dahihandy, Gudhipadwa and all Brahmin religious festival are celebrated by this first obc. They are wearing 'Janwa'. They do not have scientific attitude. They do not have awearnes about history of OBC. They are enjoying Brahmin Dharm.

Second type of OBC is known as mediator. This type of obc follows the two way. Brahmin culture and scientific culture are followed by him. He is very confused. He likes to remain middle level. He lives his life for self and family only. He do not full interest in respect of development of society.

Third type of OBC is known as Ambedkarite OBC. He is having scientific attitude, struggle full nature. He is aware about our rights. He read books of Jyotiba Fule, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar, Marks-lenin, periyar swami etc. he awake to first and second type of OBC. More than 3748 cast come under the OBC category. But they are not united. They always struggle to one another. So it is a social mechanism which is given by ruling class of India.

The period of Buddha and after:

Before independence India, there was a system of Varna. It is so ancient and old social order system. This social order system is known Varna System in the religious books i. e. Veda, Smruti, Puran etc..What is Varna ? it is nothing but a social and economical system which is run by vaidik people. Vaidik means those who have rights to read four Vedas i. e. Atharva Veda, Rugh Veda, Yejur Veda and Sam Veda. All religious book dinied right of read, teach to the people of shudras. Varna System, it is categarywise system of india i. e. Brahmin, Kshtriya, Vaishya and Shudras. This is vertical system of the society and group of people. The term 'Varna' it is word of Sanskrit language. It recognized color of people. Vern means color. First three categories(Brahmin, kshetriya vaishya) are having one and same color white(Gora). The rest people of varna, Shudra Varna is having black(kala) color. so white and black people's system was existing in india. Brahmin + Kshatriya+Vaishya against Shudra, this system is existence in modern India. They are fighting to get administrative power, ruling power. Now a day's lot of problems is made in India by the social economic order system (Varna) of religious book.

All religious books are challenged by the scientist people, Fule Shahu periyar and Ambedkarrite people, constitution of india, communist people etc. the problem of education, employment, business , education reservation equality, fraternity justice etc. are being affected. Ex. Issues of Gujrat state's shudrs people, issue of khairlanji murder, issue of Ramabai Ambedkar Nagar, Patel Jat and Maratha reservation issue etc. now struggle is going on in India for socio economic justice. It is happening due to lack of value base education.

In the period of Buddha and Mahavir, there were exisance Varna System. Buddha was against to this brahminical social order system. He denied Varna system. Because he founded out that, there is no equality, not right to take education to the shudras, no right to accumulate wealth etc. only shudra should have done their decided work as per brahminical religious book. Shudras and all women of india were treated as slave. Buddha is pioneer of socio economic justice in the world. He awaked the shudras, enlightened them, integrated them in the against of Varna System of Brahmin. He become success and established equality, justice, fraternity and independence. Finally the Buddha destroyed the Varna system. Emperor Chandragupt Mourya, Emperor Bindusar, Emperor Ashok, Emperor Brihidrath etc. all these emperors run the buddhas' philosophy in their working period. After merder of emperor Brahidrath by Brahmin pushyamitra shung, shudras people were classified into cast subcast by the Brahmin. Vertical system was implimanted for cast and sub cast. Cast means a small group of shudras' people. Cast wise job are nominated and

created as per religious books of Brahmin by Das bodh(Ramdas Swami), Dnyaneshwari (Dnyaneshwar, Manusmriti (Bhargav) Ramayan (Valmiki) etc. it was so difficult to awake and enlighten to the thousand of cast and sub cast (Sudras). Buddha was succeed to integrate the shudras in the name of shudra. Because there were only one category or Varna i. e. Shudra.

After murder of last mौरya emperor Brahadrath, shudra were divided into cast and sub cast. In modern india, Ati shudras varn was created, which is known as non religious people. Those who have not any religion, any rights. They were called slave. Which has been kept at the bottom of four varnas. Total number of cast in shudras is more than 7000. . In modern India, it was very difficult to integrate thousand of casts and thousand of sub casts' people. Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar found concept to integrate all cast of shudras. Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar integrated them in the name of Other Backward Classes, Schedule cast, schedule tribe. These are 85% population of the India which is integrated in the name of OBC, SC, & ST. these people are put out of ruling power, administrative power, from share in industries, trade etc. thus these people were made depended people and slave people of modern India.

Before and After Independence of India

Before 1947, Britishers were running the government. First three varna getting benefits from britishers. But britisher's principle of equality before law is denied by the Brahmin. Because there is no any discrimination. There is no any great and beggar by birth, there no any Brahmin and shudras. All is equal before law. Brahmin mentality is, there should not be right of education, jobs and reservation to shudras' people. The should be kept as per religion and its books. First three Varna opposed to britishers' equality policies. They created campaigning in the society in the name of freedom. It was a conspiracy of first three vara. People of India accepted the policy of freedom. The shudras and ati shudras were kept from conspiracy and used them in the name of freedom. Why did not Jyotiba Fule, the king shahuji, Dr, Babasaheb Ambedkar, Periyar Ramaswami take participation in freedom movement of Brahmin?

After 1947, transfer of power came in the hands of Brahmin kshatriya and vaishya. Congress, BJP, Communist all these are nationalize Parties. One Brahmin parti remains in ruling and second one BJP remains in opposition. Communist brahminical parti help them to establish government. thus 3.5% foreigner run the India. Till date they are in power. Where is freedom of India(shudras) ? they are being put depended and demanding people only.

Economic System:

There are three types of economy in the world.

- 1) Capitalist economy (capitalism)
- 2) Socialist economy (socialism)
- 3) Mixed economy (welfarism)

India accepted mixed economy. We should have accepted socialist economy. Because India has base of Buddha's philosophy. All the resources are captured by first here Varna. Due to this, mixed economy have been accepted but the ratio of both economy I. e. capitalist and socialist was not fixed. Now a days, capitalist ratio is being increased year by year. All government sector are being privatized in the name of economic policy. Those people have lot of resources i. e. wealth, land, power, trade, business, governing power etc. they are putting control over the socio economic system. That is way, mixed economy is being transferred into capitalist economy. The existence of democratic country is being abolished by implementing new economic policy of 1991. Liberalization, privatization, globalization, foreign direct

investment, special economic zones etc. are economic policies. In the name of these policies, SC, ST, OBC people are being kept far away from ruling power, administration power, judiciary power, media power etc.

Problems-challenges in Independence India

- 1) Ruling class has adopted and implemented new economic system of 1991 to enforce slavery on SC ST OBC.
- 2) Bipolar system: the system of liberalization, privatization, globalization, SEZ, FDI in which ruling class have started a bipolar system with collaboration of ruling and opposition parties. For instance, UPA if formed by congress and NDA is formed by BJP and using this bipolar system. They are controlling all regional parties and have made them depended on them.
- 3) Judicial System: judiciary is one of the four pillars of democracy. Due to lack of the representation of SC/ST/OBC and minorities, judiciary goes against constitution and gives decision in favor of the three varna (Upper class).
- 4) Nexalite and Terrorism: in the name of terrorism, ruling class has created fear psychosis in all Muslims by falsely arresting some innocent Muslim youth. And keeping them behind bar. In the name of naxalite, ruling class captured forest, land of tribes. Schedule tribes are being landless.
- 5) 5th & 6th schedule of constitution: schedule tribes are targeted by not implementing the 5th and 6th schedule of constitution of India.
- 6) Foreign Direct Investment: in the name of FDI, Indian land is being sold. Ruling class are destroying small and medium industries.
- 7) Contract System: it a part of capitalist system. This has been enforced to exploit all workers. Total remuneration is not given to workers.
- 8) Devaluation of Indian currency: year by year, the Indian currency are being devaluated by the new economic system.
- 9) Farmer committing suicide: the best climate for agriculture is available in India. In spite of this, lakhs of farmers committed suicide in last 70 years.
- 10) Cast based senses: ruling class do not cast based senses. It is basic requirement to give representation in all sectors in the ratio of population. OBC cast based senses is not being made by ruling class.
- 11) Not proper use of reservation policy: the article no. 340,341,342 on the constitution of India is not being implemented honestly by ruling class. That's why, it creates discrimination.

Effect of Ruling Class or Brahmin Bureaucracy:

So many negative effects are coming. New economic policies, reservation policies, employment policies etc. are affected by racial discrimination theory of ruling class. Following information will help to clear the reality of ruling class or Brahmin bureaucracy.

Table no. 1. Effect of wrong economic policy of 1991

Year	Dollar	Devaluation of Indian Rupees
1991	1	24.47
1997	1	36.06
1999	1	48
2013	1	61
2014	1	63

2015	1	65
2016	1	68
2018	1	74.5
2021	1	73.90

Source: book-Indian economy/different news paper

The above table no 1 shows that Indian currency is not in strong position. It is becoming devalued year by year. Where is the merit of three varnas? They are ruling from 1947 to till date. All efforts are done only to keep aside SC ST OBC and minority from power and a decision is taken in favor of Brahmin Kshatriya and Vaishya. They are running government only for their communities.

Discrimination policy by Ruling Class (first three Varna)

Table no. 2. Conspiracy in interview by Brahmin class

Ayurved Medical Officer Exam 2013 final result

Sr. No-244/07/2015/chayan

Indore date 3 Dec. 2015

Sr. No.	Roll No.	Merit No.	Name of Candidate	M /F	Class	Return exam marks	Interview marks	Total
696	102613	10	Mukesh Bhayal	M	OBC	333	15	348
1569	105697	51	Ravindra Sharma	M	GEN	309	29	338
804	102997	45	Dipesh sing kathota	M	OBC	324	14	338
1168	104262	59	Sanjya sahu	M	OBC	324	12	336
585	102195	65	Surendra patel	M	OBC	321	14	335
1019	103796	95	Neha kohali	F	GEN	306	27	333
1031	103820	94	Kanika singh kharpuse	F	GEN	306	27	333
876	103280	83	Arvind sahu	M	OBC	318	15	333
1458	105280	82	Denish hammad	M	OBC	321	12	333
1472	105338	101	Ankita chaube	F	GEN	306	26	332
975	103642	96	Manish rai	M	OBC	318	14	332
1245	104539	108	Jitendra jain	M	GEN	303	28	331
1649	106052	107	Nidhi Mishra	F	GEN	306	22	328
884	103311	104	Aditya nema	M	OBC	315	16	331
1567	105704	134	Nidhi dubey	F	GEN	306	22	328
938	103510	126	Mrudul jaiswal	F	OBC	312	16	328
1503	105431	125	Rita malviya	F	OBC	315	13	328
761	102844	155	Bharat Sharma	M	GEN	300	27	327
1022	103803	154	Priyanka jain	F	GEN	300	27	327
1712	106289	153	Shashikant duwvdi	M	GEN	300	27	327
429	101604	156	Anil yadav	M	OBC	312	14	326
960	103595	186	Ashitosh diwvedi	F	GEN	297	28	325
449	101665	182	Ravi Shankar shukla	M	GEN	300	25	325
1615	105934	183	Abhishek tiwari	M	GEN	300	25	325
1619	105943	170	Rahul chourasiya	M	OBC	315	10	325
331	101235	198	Vaidhi chourasiya	F	GEN	300	24	324
821	103058	188	Arjun potidar	M	OBC	312	12	324

1761	106488	189	Vidhya anjana	F	OBC	312	12	324
1239	104509	205	Chaya thakur	F	OBC	309	14	323
1512	105476	202	Sandip yamde	M	OBC	309	14	323
1606	105886	203	Rahul nikum	M	OBC	309	14	323
1688	106193	228	Omprakash shukla	M	GEN	297	25	322
1463	105301	225	Rahul jain	M	GEN	300	22	322
408	101519	253	Ashish raje	M	GEN	297	24	321
220	100835	232	Dipak sisodiya	M	OBC	309	12	321
702	102633	234	Uma kushwah	F	OBC	309	12	321
1080	103975	231	Ranjana rai	F	OBC	309	12	321
1538	105576	233	Lucky chourasiya	M	OBC	309	12	321

Source: Ayurved Medical Officer Exam 2013 final result

Table no. 3. Analysis of table no. 2

OBC Candidate	OBC's Marks in Interview	General Candidate	Open's Marks in Interview
Mukesh Bhayal	15	Ravindra Sharma	29
Dipesh sing kathota	14	Neha kohali	27
Sanjya sahu	12	Kanika singh kharpuse	27
Denish hammad	12	Ankita chaube	26
Rita malviya	13	Bharat Sharma	27
Rahul chourasiya	10	Priyanka jain	27
Dipak sisodiya	12	Shashikant diwvedi	27
Uma kushwah	12	Ravi Shankar shukla	25
Ranjana rai	12	Abhishek tiwari	25
Lucky chourasiya	12	Ashitosh diwvedi	28

Above table shows the discrimination in interview. OBC's candidate have been given 10 to 15 marks and general (Brahmin ksatriya vaishya) have been given 25 to 29 marks. Upper class Brahmin selects their community candidate. It is nothing but racial discrimination. This is always being done by first three Varna.

Table no. 4 Number of employee in central services

year	No. of ministry / Department	OBC Population in India	Real position of OBC in ministry / Department	Unreserved
2012	78	52 %	17 %	58 %
2013	76	52 %	18 %	57 %
2014	71	52 %	19 %	55 %
2015	59	52 %	18 %	56 %
2016	33	52 %	14 %	60 %

Source: RTI report 2016

Table no. 4 explains the representation position of OBC in modern bureaucracy which is powerless. This is mechanism of ruling class in India. Only 14% representation has been given to 52% OBC. It says the discrimination by Brahmin

bureaucracy.

Remedies: there is very simple and result oriented solution to all problems is to sincere implication of constitution of India. It is way to live peaceful. It gives social justice, fraternity, independence, equality. The base of socio economic is derived from Buddha's philosophy. It is good for nation, it is good for human being, it is good for becoming super power country.

Conclusion: Indian people are classified into four category i. e. Brahmin, kshetriya, vaishya and shudra(abc). These four categories were called four Varna. Out of this first three varna had a right of education. The fourth varna shudra which population is 85% in India has been denied and sacked education from them. Since independence, as the political power went in the hands of foreigner / upper class. They became policy makers of the country. They are trying to convert mixed economy into capitalist economy with the help of new education policy. They are trying to reestablish varna system in new form in the name of new economic policies. Socio economic development along with Indian constitution is being neglected. As per Arjun sen gupta, below poverty line is increasing. 77% population have come under the below poverty line and new hunger line is being created by new economic policy along with education policy. 73% wealth of India under control the merely 1% people of India this is result of education policy and their policy makers. 2020 education policy has no pace of reservation representation to the SC ST OBC class. They will suffer in future. To having 100% implementation of Indian constitution is remedy to this.

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